

ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING A PHYTOGEL BASED ON PURSLANE**Baurzhanova A.S.****Tleubaeva M.I.**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17332857>

Relevance: herbal preparations are in high demand due to their safety and biological activity. Purslane (*Portulaca oleracea*) is a promising source of anti-inflammatory and antioxidant compounds, making it an attractive candidate for phytogel development. The use of stable gelling agents can ensure stability, prolonged release of organic compounds, and improved processing properties. The development of a purslane-based phytogel offers both scientific and practical innovation, as well as economic value, as it is expected to expand the range of domestically produced preparations and reduce dependence on imported products.

Purpose of the study: develop a business plan for the production of purslane-based phytogel using an innovative gelling agent and evaluate its pharmaceutical and economic feasibility.

Materials and methods: the study included an economic analysis, including a market assessment for herbal preparations, a cost analysis, price assurance, and financial forecasting. Financial analysis methods, such as break-even point calculations, profitability analysis, and investment attractiveness analysis, were used.

Results: an economic analysis of the pharmaceutical production of purslane-based phytogel using an innovative gelling agent was conducted. A business plan was developed, including cost calculations, sales price formation, and financial performance forecasts. The data obtained confirmed the economic feasibility and profitability of the project.

Conclusions: the study demonstrated that the development of purslane-based phytogel using an innovative gelling agent has potential for successful implementation in the pharmaceutical market. The project's economic feasibility and high profitability open up opportunities for investment and further development of the domestic pharmaceutical industry. Implementation of this project will not only expand the range of herbal remedies but also strengthen the pharmaceutical sector's independence from imported goods, a necessary step for ensuring the industry's development.